

MICROSTRUCTURAL CONTROL DURING THERMOMECHANICAL PROCESSING OF DISCONTINUOUSLY REINFORCED TITANIUM COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Ti-6Al-4V discontinuously reinforced with 10 vol.% TiB whiskers produced by a prealloyed powder metallurgy route was considered in this study. The deformation behavior of this composite was evaluated over wide temperature and strain rate ranges (900–1200°C, 10^{-3} – 10 s⁻¹) with the help of isothermal constant strain rate compression tests. Detailed analyses of the test data were conducted to identify various microstructural mechanisms over these ranges by applying various materials modeling techniques and a process map for hot working was developed. In the $\alpha+\beta$ range, the material exhibits fine-grained superplasticity at slow strain rates ($< 10^{-1}$ s⁻¹) which occurs by grain boundary sliding accommodated by diffusional flow. The β phase deforms by dynamic recrystallization at slow strain rates and the activation energy for this process is close to that for self-diffusion in β -Ti. At high strain rates (>1 s⁻¹), adiabatic shear banding occurs in the $\alpha+\beta$ range while cavitation in the matrix as well as at the interface occurs in the β range, and these processing conditions must be avoided to obtain microstructural control. The deformation mechanisms of the Ti-6Al-4V discontinuously reinforced with TiB produced by the prealloyed powder route are found to be similar to that of the unreinforced Ti-6Al-4V.

Key Terms: titanium, whisker, hot deformation, microstructure, mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced titanium composites are emerging as potential candidates for replacing structural components requiring high specific properties at room as well as moderately elevated temperatures [1]. Among all the possible reinforcement phases for titanium, TiB provides the best balance of stiffness, stability, and similarity of thermal expansion coefficient [2]. The major advantages of TiB reinforced titanium include reaction-free interface and ease of workability. Recent advances in the synthesis techniques enable production of these composites with consistent properties in a cost-effective manner. A variety of techniques such as conventional casting, powder metallurgy, rapid solidification, and mechanical alloying have been used to produce these composites, and the final microstructural characteristics (e.g. grain size and morphology, TiB size, morphology, and distribution) sensitively depend on the processing method. Thermomechanical processing (TMP) is not only an essential step in the shape-forming of engineering components, but also causes significant modifications in the microstructure and a gamut of enhanced mechanical property combinations can be obtained. The objective of this effort is to study the influence of TMP on the microstructural evolution in discontinuously reinforced titanium over wide temperature and strain rate ranges with a view to optimize the processing parameters to obtain desired microstructures. Material modeling techniques involving analysis of flow stress data were used to achieve this objective and the deformation mechanism interpretations were validated with microstructural observations and ductility measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ti-6Al-4V has been chosen as the matrix alloy in this study. Prealloyed powder of boron-modified Ti-6Al-4V was prepared by inert gas atomization. Boron additions to the melt were made in the form of TiB₂ which dissolves in the liquid melt and forms TiB during solidification by an eutectic reaction. The melt practice consisted of adding appropriate amounts of Ti, Al-V master alloy, and TiB₂ for obtaining Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB composite. The final chemical composition (in wt%) is 6.13Al, 4.16V, 1.46B, 0.19O, 0.15C, 0.053Fe, and balance Ti. Prealloyed powder (size < 150 μm) of about 1 kg was packed inside a thick-walled (6.35 mm) can that was 70 mm in diameter and 130 mm long made of commercial purity Ti, vacuum outgassed at 300°C for 24 h, and sealed. The can was heated to 1200°C, soaked for 1 h, and then blind-die compacted in an extrusion chamber heated to 260°C. The billet height was reduced by about 30% at a ram speed of 6.35 mm s⁻¹, the compact was held at a pressure of 1400 MPa for 180 s, and subsequently air-cooled to room temperature.

Cylindrical specimens of 10 mm diameter and 15 mm height were machined from the compact via electro-discharge machining (EDM) and the surface was grind finished to remove the EDM recast layer. Uniaxial compression tests were conducted using a computer-controlled servohydraulic testing machine. An induction coil and susceptor setup was used to heat the specimen and the platens. The specimens were coated with a glass paste for lubrication and environmental protection. Concentric grooves of 0.1 mm depth were machined on the top and bottom surfaces for retaining the lubricant during testing. A thermocouple was soldered to the specimen to monitor and control the temperature of the specimen. Adiabatic temperature rise (significant at strain rates above 10⁻¹ s⁻¹) was also recorded using this thermocouple. Tests were conducted in the temperature range 900–1200°C at 50°C intervals. Even though boron is reported to be an α stabilizer, the boron solid solubility in α-titanium is extremely small (<0.1 at.%) [3] and the β-transus is not expected to increase significantly compared to that of the Ti-6Al-4V (~1010°C). Therefore, the selected temperature range covers both the α+β and β phase fields. Specimens were heated to the test temperature, soaked for 15 min for equilibration, and deformed at a predetermined strain rate. A range of constant true strain rates, viz. 10⁻³, 10⁻², 10⁻¹, 1, and 10 s⁻¹ were used in the present investigation. This wide strain rate range is selected which covers the press speeds encountered in a majority of the bulk metalworking processes including forging, extrusion, and rolling. Specimens were deformed to half of their original height in each case and were air-cooled to room temperature. The load-stroke data obtained were converted to true stress-true plastic strain using the standard method. The flow stress σ was corrected for adiabatic temperature rise according to the relation $\sigma \propto \exp(-Q/RT)$, where Q is the activation energy, R is gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature. Hot tensile tests were also conducted at selected temperatures and an initial strain rate of 10⁻³ s⁻¹ (constant crosshead speed of 0.02 mm s⁻¹) using 2.5 mm thick flat dog-bone shaped specimens of 19 mm gage length and 5.6 mm gage width. Specimens were coated with glass lubricant, tested in air, and elongation to failure was recorded. Selected specimens were sectioned after deformation parallel to the compression axis and the cut surface was prepared for microstructural examination using standard metallographic techniques. Microstructural observations were made in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) in the backscatter electron imaging mode. Microstructural measurements were performed by digital image analysis techniques.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Starting Microstructure

The initial microstructure of the Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB after blind-die compaction is shown in Fig. 1. The microstructure consisted of equiaxed α grains with an average grain size of 3 μm with a retained β volume fraction of 12% decorating the grain boundaries. The TiB comprised of 10±1 vol.% and the majority of the TiB (~8.5 vol.%) is present as eutectic needles with an average length of 10 μm and an

aspect ratio of 10. Careful examination of the microstructure at high magnifications revealed the presence of submicron size whiskers of TiB of about 1.5 vol.% with an average length of 0.5 μm and aspect ratio of 10. A few isolated coarse particles of primary TiB are also present in this material whose volume fraction is very low. The TiB is uniformly distributed and randomly oriented in the matrix.

Fig. 1 Backscatter SEM image of the starting microstructure of the Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB compact. The gray background is the α matrix, the bright phase is β , and the dark phase is TiB.

Stress-Strain Behavior

The shapes of the flow curves exhibited by the material at different temperatures and strain rates of testing can be broadly classified into three categories, viz. flow softening, steady-state, and oscillatory; and curves representative of these features are shown in Fig. 2. In the $\alpha+\beta$ temperature range (Fig. 2a), continuous flow softening after a peak stress was observed at strain rates at or below 1 s^{-1} while a rapid drop in flow stress and oscillatory behavior was observed at 10 s^{-1} . In the β range (Fig. 2b), flat stress-strain curves were observed at slow strain rates ($<10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), which are indicative of steady-state flow behavior, while at high strain rates ($\geq 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) flow softening and oscillatory behavior was observed. Although, shapes of the stress-strain curves indicate changes in the flow behavior with strain rate in both the $\alpha+\beta$ and β phase fields, no conclusions regarding the mechanisms of deformation can be made since different processes can exhibit similar stress-strain features [4]. For example, flow softening type curves may indicate dynamic recrystallization or flow localization. Therefore, further analysis of strain rate and temperature sensitivity of flow stress is required to evaluate the mechanisms of hot deformation.

Activation Analysis

The strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ and temperature T dependence of the steady-state flow stress σ during hot deformation is generally expressed in terms of Arrhenius type rate equation [4]

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A \sigma^n \exp(-Q/RT) \quad (1)$$

where n is the stress exponent, A is a material constant, Q is the activation energy, and R is the gas constant. In order to identify the mechanism of hot deformation, the activation parameters n and Q are to

Fig. 2 Stress-strain curves of Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB compact at different strain rates and in the (a) $\alpha+\beta$ phase field (900°C) and (b) β phase field (1200°C).

be evaluated. The variation of σ vs. $\dot{\epsilon}$ at different temperatures is shown in Fig. 3(a) on a log-log plot. The inverse of the slope of this variation represents n . From Fig. 3(a), it is seen that n is strain rate dependent when considered over the entire strain rate range employed in this study. The temperature dependence of the flow stress at different strain rates is shown in Fig. 3(b) on a semi-log plot. The variation shows a clear change in the slope in the $\alpha+\beta$ and β phase fields indicating that different deformation mechanisms are operating in these two phase fields. It should be noted that Eq. (1) does not include the influence of microstructural parameters such as β volume fraction, grain size, and TiB size that may change during TMP.

Processing Map

The flow stress data is analyzed further using the approach of processing maps described elsewhere [5] to evaluate the constitutive behavior of Ti-6Al-4V/TiB compact during hot deformation. A processing map, depicted in a frame of temperature and strain rate, consists of a superimposition of a power dissipation efficiency (PDE) map and an instability map. The PDE map represents the pattern in which the input power ($\sigma \dot{\epsilon}$) is dissipated by the material through microstructural changes rather than heat. The rate of this change normalized with respect to an ideal linear power dissipator (strain rate sensitivity $m=1$) is given by the dimensionless parameter known as efficiency of power dissipation η defined as $2m/(m+1)$. An instability map is developed using the continuum criterion given by

$$\xi(\dot{\epsilon}) = \frac{\partial \ln\left(\frac{m}{m+1}\right)}{\partial \ln \dot{\epsilon}} + m < 0 \quad (2)$$

Flow instabilities are predicted to occur when the dimensionless instability parameter ξ becomes negative. The processing map developed for Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB compact at a true plastic strain of 0.5 is shown in Fig. 4. Maps at lower strains exhibited essentially similar features. The map exhibits three domains: (A) one at high strain rates in the $\alpha+\beta$ range, (B) one at slow strain rates in the $\alpha+\beta$ range, and (C) one at slow strain rates in the β range; and a regime of flow instability at higher strain rates in the β range.

Fig. 3 Plot of (a) σ vs. $\dot{\epsilon}$ and (b) σ vs. $1/T$ for Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB compact.

Fig. 4 Processing map obtained on Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB compact at a true plastic strain of 0.5. The contour numbers represent percent efficiency of power dissipation. The bold line represents the boundary of the instability regime evaluated using the continuum criteria given in Eq. (2).

Domain A: The high strain rate domain in the $\alpha+\beta$ range occurs in the strain rate range $1-10\text{ s}^{-1}$ and temperature range $900-1000^\circ\text{C}$ with a peak η of 52% and η increases steeply with increase in strain rate and decrease in temperature. Such features are typically observed to represent a fracture process in several materials [6]. A macro picture of a specimen deformed at $900^\circ\text{C}/10\text{ s}^{-1}$ is shown in Fig. 5(a) which exhibits shear bands at an angle approximately 45° to the compression axis. The intensity of these bands decreased with increase in temperature and decrease in strain rate. The formation of these bands is attributed to the adiabatic conditions created. The temperature rise (ΔT) recorded at different temperatures and strain rates of testing are reported in Table 1. A ΔT as high as 43°C was recorded at $900^\circ\text{C}/10\text{ s}^{-1}$. The heat generated during high strain rate deformation does not conduct away due to insufficient time and low thermal conductivity of titanium, which reduces the flow stress locally leading to flow localization and fracture. Therefore, higher strain rates are to be avoided during $\alpha+\beta$ processing of the composite for obtaining defect-free microstructures.

Table 1 Temperature rise ($^\circ\text{C}$) recorded during compression testing of Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB

Strain rate, s^{-1}	Temperature, $^\circ\text{C}$						
	900	950	1000	1050	1100	1150	1200
10^{-3}	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10^{-2}	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10^{-1}	8	6	3	0	0	0	0
1	24	19	11	9	6	4	2
10	43	28	22	16	12	9	7

Domain B: The low strain rate domain in the $\alpha+\beta$ range occurs in the strain rate range $10^{-3}-10^{-1}\text{ s}^{-1}$ with a peak η of 60% occurring at $900^\circ\text{C}/10^{-3}\text{ s}^{-1}$. This domain appears to extend to lower temperatures and strain rates than those employed in the present study. High η values in this domain, which correspond to a strain rate sensitivity in the range 0.4–0.5, confirm that the material exhibits superplastic flow under these processing conditions. The occurrence of superplasticity is best demonstrated by large tensile ductility values. Tensile specimen deformed at 900°C and an initial strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} did not show any indications of failure even after an elongation of 145%, which further confirms the superplasticity in this domain. The microstructure of a specimen deformed in compression at $900^\circ\text{C}/10^{-3}\text{ s}^{-1}$ is shown in Fig. 5(b). The features to be noted in this microstructure are i) the α grain size after deformation is essentially unchanged compared to the starting material (Fig. 1), and ii) the β phase is present at the grain boundary triple junctions. The mechanism of superplasticity involves sliding of grain boundaries with simultaneous relaxation of the stresses generated at the boundaries and triple junctions by processes involving diffusional flow or plastic deformation. TiB and the β phase at the grain boundary triple junctions are responsible for providing a stable fine-grained microstructure by restricting grain growth, which is the most important requirement for superplasticity. As for the relaxation of the stresses developed during grain boundary sliding, the deformation behavior of the β phase present at the triple junctions will be the controlling factor. At high temperatures, bcc β can exhibit thermally activated relaxation processes such as cross-slip or diffusional creep. The values of activation parameters (n and Q) estimated using Eq. (1) in this $T-\dot{\epsilon}$ window are given in Table 2. The apparent activation energy estimated during superplastic deformation (377 kJ/mol) is much higher than that for self-diffusion in β (153 kJ/mol) [7], which suggests that dynamic recovery by cross-slip is the rate-controlling step. The composite behavior under these temperature and strain rate conditions is very similar to that of the unreinforced Ti-6Al-4V with an equiaxed $\alpha+\beta$ starting microstructure [8]. Superplastic forming is a well established process in Ti-6Al-4V, which is often coupled with diffusion bonding to form components with intricate shapes [9].

Fig. 5 Microstructures of Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB compact specimens deformed in compression at (a) $900^{\circ}\text{C}/10 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (macrograph, etched with Kroll's reagent), (b) $900^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (backscatter SEM image) (c) $1200^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (backscatter SEM image) and (d) $1200^{\circ}\text{C}/10 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (backscatter SEM image). The compression axis is vertical in all the micrographs.

Table 2 Activation parameters estimated for Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB

Phase Field	n	Q , kJ/mol
$\alpha+\beta$	3.3	377
β	3.6	208

Domain C: The slow strain rate domain in the β range occurs in the strain rate ranges 10^{-3} – 10^{-1} s^{-1} with a peak η of $\sim 50\%$ at $1200^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This domain also does not seem to be fully developed in the tested T – $\dot{\epsilon}$ ranges and is likely to expand to lower $\dot{\epsilon}$ and higher T . Moderately high η and steady-state flow curves (Fig. 2b) indicate that the β phase exhibits dynamic recrystallization (DRX). A microstructure of a specimen deformed at $1200^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is shown in Fig. 5(c) which shows a fully lamellar $\alpha+\beta$ structure. Cooling across the β –transus after deformation causes changes in the microstructure and the features of β -DRX could not be captured. The tensile elongation recorded at $1200^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is 68%, which further supports the interpretation of DRX in β phase. The activation parameters estimated in this domain are

also reported in Table 2. The activation energy is close to that for self-diffusion in β -Ti (153 kJ/mol) [7], which indicates that diffusion is the rate-controlling step during DRX of the β phase. The deformation behavior of Ti-6Al-4V/TiB composite produced by the prealloyed powder route in the β phase is similar to that of Ti-6Al-4V which also exhibits DRX though at lower temperatures [8].

Flow Instability: In the β phase field, the instability criterion predicts a flow instability regime in the ranges 1160-1200°C and 1–10 s⁻¹. A microstructure of a specimen deformed at 1200°C and 10 s⁻¹ is shown in Fig. 5(d), which shows that the flow instabilities are manifested in the form of cavitation in the matrix as well as at the interface (indicated by arrows). At fast strain rates, there is insufficient time for the accommodation of plastic flow by diffusion, which causes cavitation.

CONCLUSIONS

Hot deformation behavior of a Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB compact prepared from prealloyed powder was characterized with the help of hot compression tests in the temperature range 900-1200°C and strain rate range 10⁻³–10 s⁻¹. The data were analyzed using available materials models and the following conclusions are drawn from this study:

- The material exhibits fine-grained superplasticity in the α + β temperature range at slow strain rates (<10⁻¹ s⁻¹). A stable fine grain size is maintained due to the presence of TiB and superplasticity occurs by grain boundary sliding accommodated by diffusional flow.
- The β phase undergoes dynamic recrystallization at strain rates below 10⁻¹ s⁻¹ and the apparent activation energy for β -DRX is close to that for self diffusion in the β -titanium.
- At strain rates above 1 s⁻¹, adiabatic shear banding occurs in the α + β range, while matrix and interface cavitation occurs in the β range. These processing conditions must be avoided in order to obtain desirable microstructures.
- The composite behavior is found to be similar to that of the unreinforced Ti-6Al-4V and the material offers wide temperature and strain rate ranges for shape-forming without generating defects.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was conducted as part of in-house research of the Metallic Composites research group of the Materials and Manufacturing Directorate, Air Force Research Laboratory. Two of the authors (ST and RBB) were supported under the auspices of Air Force Contract F33615-99-C-5803. The assistance of P.N. Fagin in performing the compression testing and R. Ravi in conducting the data analysis is greatly appreciated.

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